

Acontias occidentalis Western burrowing skink

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Reptile

Size: 20-30 cm (total body length)

Distribution:

Republic of South Africa (Limpopo Province), Zimbabwe, Namibia and South Angola

Importance:

Acontias occidentalis is a Southern African endemic legless skink that represents a highly specialized fossorial lineage within the region. It contributes to soil ecosystem processes and reflects unique evolutionary adaptations to subterranean life. Sequencing its genome enables study of limb loss and body elongation, improves skink phylogenetic resolution, and provides essential genomic resources for conservation and detection of cryptic diversity.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 90.09 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 5.17 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 2.38 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 98.0%, Duplicated: 1.6%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 964.52 kilobases

Contig number: 9 137

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